

ENHANCING REPRODUCTIVE SUCCESS IN CATTLE: THE ROLE OF EARLY PREGNANCY DETECTION AND PREGNANCY-ASSOCIATED GLYCOPROTEINS (PAGS)

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ABSTRACT

Reproductive efficiency is vital for sustainable and profitable beef and dairy farming. Early detection of pregnancy and failure minimizes reproductive losses and optimizes herd productivity. Pregnancy-associated glycoproteins (PAGs), secreted by embryonic trophoblast cells, are reliable biomarkers detectable in maternal circulation as early as 24 days post-insemination. PAGs provide accurate early pregnancy diagnosis and insights into embryo viability and placental health. Despite challenges like postpartum interference and logistical constraints, advancements in assay technologies and ongoing research continue to enhance their role in improving reproductive outcomes.

Keywords: Reproductive efficiency, pregnancy diagnosis, pregnancy-associated glycoproteins (PAGs), cattle, bovine reproduction.

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